

Formulation And Evaluation Of Herbal Anti-Aging Face Serum Containing Bakuchiol And Fenugreek Extract

Tanuja Sonawane^{1*}, Shruti Bhujbal¹, Bhagyashri Khokrale¹, Dhanashri Soge¹, Amol Kumbhar², Aachal Chimkar³, Sonali Sonawane³

¹B. Pharm Students, RJSPM College of Pharmacy, Dudulgaon, Moshi, Pune, Maharashtra, India – 412105

²Principal RJSPM College of Pharmacy, Dudulgaon, Moshi, Pune, Maharashtra, India – 412105.

³Assistant Professor (M.Pharm Pharmaceutics), RJSPM College of Pharmacy, Dudulgaon, Moshi, Pune, Maharashtra, India – 412105.

ABSTRACT

Skin aging is a complex biological process influenced by intrinsic and extrinsic factors such as oxidative stress, ultraviolet (UV) radiation, and environmental pollution, which lead to the formation of free radicals and degradation of skin structure^(1,41). The present study aimed to formulate and evaluate a herbal face serum containing bakuchiol and fenugreek extracts, which are known for their antioxidant and anti-aging properties^(30,31,21). Three different formulations (F1, F2, F3, F4, F5, F6) were prepared using Carbopol 940 as a gelling agent and evaluated for various physicochemical parameters including appearance, colour, homogeneity, spreadability, pH, viscosity, and stability. In addition, antioxidant activity was assessed to determine the effectiveness of the formulations^(21,38). Among the three formulations, F5 showed superior performance with good appearance, smooth texture, excellent homogeneity, appropriate pH, and better spreadability. It also exhibited higher antioxidant activity compared to F1, F2, F3, F4 and F6, indicating improved efficacy against oxidative stress^(21,38). The study concludes that the developed herbal face serum is stable, safe, and effective, and has significant potential as a natural anti-aging skincare product^(42,47).

Keywords: Bakuchiol, Fenugreek extract, Herbal face serum, Anti-aging, Antioxidant activity, Viscosity.

INTRODUCTION

The skin is the largest organ of the human body and serves as a protective barrier against environmental factors like pollution, microorganisms, and UV radiation⁽⁵⁾. It also plays an important role in appearance and confidence. Prolonged exposure to sunlight and pollution can cause dryness, wrinkles, and premature aging^(1,41). Structurally, the skin consists of three layers—epidermis, dermis, and hypodermis—which maintain hydration, elasticity, and firmness⁽⁵⁾. Skin aging results from intrinsic (genetic) and extrinsic factors such as UV exposure and pollution, leading to collagen degradation and reduced elasticity^(1,4). Oxidative stress and free radicals significantly contribute to this process⁽⁴¹⁾. Herbal cosmetics are increasingly preferred due to their safety and natural origin^(43,45). Face serums are popular for their lightweight nature and efficient

delivery of active ingredients^(42,47). This study focuses on a herbal face serum containing bakuchiol and fenugreek extracts. Bakuchiol acts as a natural retinol alternative with anti-aging effects^(30,31), while fenugreek provides antioxidant and moisturizing benefits^(21,23). Limited research exists on their combined use, highlighting the need for this formulation and evaluation.

1. MATERIAL AND METHOD

All chemicals and excipients used were of analytical grade. Bakuchiol was obtained from VedaOils Pvt. Ltd., India, while fenugreek extract (*Trigonella foenum-graecum L.*) was procured from Purenso Select, India. Distilled water was used in this study.

➤ Materials

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Table no. 1 : Physicochemical Properties of Excipients Used.

Sr. No.	Excipient	Nature / Type	Appearance	Solubility	Melting / Boiling Point	pH (1% sol.)	Role in Formulation
1.	Bakuchiol	Meroterpenoid (Herbal active)	Pale yellow oily liquid	Insoluble in water, soluble in oils & alcohol	liquid	-	Anti-aging agent, antioxidant
2.	Fenugreek Extract	Herbal extract	Brownish viscous liquid	Partially soluble in water	-	5-6	Antioxidant, moisturizing agent
3.	Carbopol 940	Synthetic polymer	White fluffy powder	Dispersible in water	-	2.5-3	Gelling agent, thickener
4.	Glycerin	Polyol	Clear viscous liquid	Miscible with water & alcohol	290°C	6-7	Moisturizer, humectant
5.	Tween 80	Non-ionic surfactant	Amber viscous liquid	Soluble in water & alcohol	-	6-7	Solubilizer, emulsifier
6.	Vitamin E (Tocopherol)	Fat-soluble vitamin	Pale yellow viscous oil	Insoluble in water, soluble in oils	2-5°C	-	Antioxidant, stabilizer
7.	Rose Water	Aromatic aqueous solution	Clear liquid	Miscible with water	-	5-6	Fragrance, soothing agent
8.	Sodium Benzoate	Inorganic salt	White crystalline powder	Soluble in water	-	7-8	Preservative
9.	Triethanolamine	Organic compound	Colorless viscous liquid	Miscible with water & alcohol	-	Alkaline	pH adjuster, neutralizer

➤ METHOD

A. Preparation of Aqueous Phase:

1. Carbopol was accurately weighed and slowly dispersed in a portion of distilled water with gentle stirring.
2. The dispersion was allowed to hydrate for 30-45 min to ensure complete swelling of the polymer.
3. Glycerine was added to the hydrated Carbopol dispersion and mixed uniformly.
4. Fenugreek extract was added with continuous gentle stirring.

5. Sodium benzoate was dissolved separately in a small quantity of distilled water and added to the aqueous phase of the emulsion.

6. Triethanolamine was added dropwise to the aqueous phase with continuous stirring until gel formation occurred, and the pH was adjusted to 5.2-5.8.

B. Preparation of Oil Phase

1. Vitamin E, lemon oil, and sandalwood oil were taken in a separate beaker.
2. Tween 80 was added to the oil phase and mixed thoroughly to obtain a clear and uniform mixture.

C. Incorporation of Active Ingredient

1. Bakuchiol was added slowly to the aqueous phase during the cooling stage with gentle stirring.
2. The prepared oil phase was then added slowly to the aqueous phase with continuous gentle stirring to obtain a homogeneous solution.
3. The final volume was adjusted to 20 mL with distilled water and mixed gently to avoid air entrapment.

D. Packaging and Storage

1. The prepared formulation was transferred to a clean amber container and stored at room temperature.

Ingredients	F1 (20ml)	F2 (20ml)	F3 (20ml)	F4 (20ml)	F5 (20ml)	F6 (20ml)	Function
Bakuchiol	0.02g	0.06g	0.10g	0.02g	0.06g	0.10g	Anti-aging active
Fenugreek Extract	1ml	1ml	1ml	1ml	1ml	1ml	Herbal Active
Carbopol 940	0.02g	0.04g	0.06g	0.04g	0.06g	0.08g	Gelling Agent
Glycerine	1.4ml	1.4ml	1.4ml	8.4ml	5.4ml	1.4ml	Humectant
Tween 80	0.4ml	0.4ml	0.4ml	0.4ml	0.4ml	0.4ml	Solubilizer
Triethanolamine	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.	Q.s.	Neutralizer/pH Adjuster
Vitamin E	0.2ml	0.2ml	0.2ml	0.2ml	0.2ml	0.2ml	Antioxidant
Rose Water	0.06ml	0.06ml	0.06ml	0.06ml	0.06ml	0.06ml	Fragrance
Sodium Benzoate	0.02g	0.02g	0.02g	0.02g	0.02g	0.02g	Preservative
Distilled Water	Q.s. to 20ml	Vehicle					

Table No. 2 Formula :On Trial-And-Error Basis

EVALUATION PARAMETER	METHOD/ PROCEDURE	PURPOSE	ACCEPTANCE CRITERIA
Appearance & Colour	Visually observed for colour, clarity, and uniformity.	To check physical appearance	Should be clear, uniform, and acceptable
Odour	Smelled after applying a small amount on skin.	To evaluate fragrance	Pleasant and characteristic
Consistency	Observed by visual and touch method.	To determine texture	Smooth, semi-liquid
Texture & Homogeneity	Examined by rubbing between fingers for uniformity.	To ensure uniform distribution	No lumps, uniform mixture
Washability	Applied on skin and washed with water.	To check ease of removal	Easily washable

pH	1 ml serum diluted with 50 ml water and measured using pH meter.	To ensure skin compatibility	4.5 – 6.5
Viscosity	Brookfield viscometer using spindle 62 at 50 rpm. Values were noted after the reading stabilized within 10–90% torque.	Check serum consistency and flow.	50–2000 mPa·s; torque 10–90%.
Spreadability	2 g sample placed between slides, weight applied, time noted for separation.	To assess ease of application	Good spreadability
In vitro Antioxidant Activity	Serum mixed with KMnO ₄ solution and colour change observed.	To detect antioxidant activity	Decolourization indicates activity

Table No.3 : Evaluation Parameters**3. RESULTS****Table no.4 : Evaluation Results**

SR. NO.	INGREDIENT	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
1.	Appearance and Colour.	Slightly turbid	Clear and uniform	Slightly turbid	Clear and uniform	Clear and uniform	Slightly turbid
2.	Odour.	Pleasant rose Odour.	Pleasant rose Odour.	Pleasant rose Odour.	Pleasant rose Odour.	Pleasant rose Odour.	Pleasant rose Odour.
3.	Texture and Homogeneity	Non-uniform.	Uniform.	Non-uniform.	Uniform.	Uniform.	Uniform.
4.	Washability:	Easily washable	Easily washable	Easily washable	Easily washable	Easily washable	Easily washable
5.	pH	5.73	6.30	6.05	6.47	6.50	6.48
6.	Spreadability:	Moderate	Good	Low	Moderate	Good	Moderate
7.	Stability	Slightly stable	Stable	Slightly stable	Stable	Stable	Stable
8.	In vitro Antioxidant Activity	Moderate decrease in purple colour	Maximum decrease in purple colour	Slight decrease in purple colour	Slight decrease in purple colour	Moderate decrease in purple colour	Moderate decrease in purple colour

★ pH Test:

F1

F2

F3

F4

F6

Fig.1 pH test- Results.

★ Viscosity:

F1

F2

F3

F4

F6

Figure.2 Viscosity test- Result.

★ In-Vitro Antioxidant Assay [using KMnO_4]**Figure 4: Formulated serums****4. DISCUSSION:**

The study aimed to develop and evaluate a herbal face serum containing bakuchiol and fenugreek extract for anti-aging use. The findings showed that formulation composition plays an important role in determining physicochemical properties, stability, and overall performance [23,24,41]. Initially, three formulations (F1–F3) were prepared, followed by three modified formulations (F4–F6) to improve characteristics. All formulations were evaluated for appearance, pH, viscosity, spreadability, antioxidant activity, and stability [24,25]. Among all formulations, F5 showed superior performance. It appeared clear and uniform, indicating proper compatibility of ingredients, while some other formulations showed slight turbidity [29]. The pH of all formulations ranged from 5.73 to 6.50, which is suitable for topical application. F5 (~6.5) was

closest to normal skin pH, suggesting better compatibility and reduced chances of irritation [41]. Viscosity values ranged from 132 to 258 mPa·s, with F5 (~240 mPa·s) showing optimum consistency, ensuring both stability and ease of application [40]. Spreadability studies also confirmed that F5 had better texture and easy application due to balanced rheological properties [25]. Lower viscosity formulations were thinner, while higher viscosity formulations showed reduced spreadability. Antioxidant activity, evaluated using the KMnO_4 method, showed that F5 had higher activity, likely due to the presence of bakuchiol and fenugreek extract, which are known for their antioxidant and anti-aging effects [14,15,43]. Stability studies indicated that F5 remained stable with minimal changes, highlighting the importance of balanced formulation [42]. Overall, the combination provides synergistic anti-aging,

moisturizing, and antioxidant benefits, though further clinical studies are required to confirm long-term safety and efficacy [2,3,11,13,21].

5. CONCLUSION:

The study was conducted to formulate and evaluate a herbal face serum containing bakuchiol and fenugreek extract. The objective of developing a stable and cosmetically acceptable formulation was achieved using suitable excipients and formulation methods [23,24]. All formulations were evaluated for parameters such as appearance, pH, homogeneity, spreadability, viscosity, washability, stability, and in vitro antioxidant activity. Among them, F5 showed better overall performance in terms of physical properties, consistency, stability, and antioxidant potential [25,42]. The results indicate that bakuchiol and fenugreek extract can be effectively incorporated into a topical serum. Their antioxidant activity suggests potential in reducing oxidative stress, a key factor in skin aging [14,15,43]. However, the study was limited to preliminary and in vitro evaluations.

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